

Mediating Effect of Human Resource Capacity and Moderating Effect of Top Management Support on the Relationship between E-government Adoption and Service Delivery in Kenya's Public Sector

Christopher Ogola¹

¹ Department of Public Policy and Administration, School of Law, Arts and Social Sciences, Kenyatta University

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ABSTRACT

E-government is one of the modern ways that governments use to provide services to the public. However, in many developing countries, there is still a challenge of implementation of e-government innovations. Kenya is one of the developing countries which face the challenge of fully implementing e-government and several studies have been conducted to identify the factors that affect e-government adoption in the country. However, the studies have only focused on explanatory variables, without examining other factors which can potentially mediate or moderate the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery. This study, therefore, sought to examine the mediating effect of human resource capacity and moderating effect of top management support on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in Kenya's public sector. The study utilized closed ended questionnaires to collect data from 66 respondents. The collected data was analyzed descriptively through means and standard deviations and inferentially through correlation and regression models. The results indicated that human resource capacity has a mediating effect on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public sector. Top management support was however, found to have no moderating effect on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public sector. The study concluded that human resource capacity is a mediating variable while top management support is an explanatory variable in the context of e-government adoption and service delivery in Kenya's public sector. The study recommended that future researchers should further explore the other factors which mediate or moderate the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the public sector.

1. Introduction

E-government, also called electronic government, is the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) to effectively and efficiently deliver government services to citizens, other public departments and businesses (United Nations, 2020). According to Broom (2015), electronic government is the use of technological communication devices, such as computers and the Internet, to provide public services to citizens in a given country or region. Moreover, other definitions given by OECD member countries reveal that e-government is the application of modern technologies in the functions and procedures of the government with the purpose of promoting efficiency, transparency and citizen participation in the government decision making processes.

Traditionally, e-government has been considered as the use of ICTs for improving and providing government services online (United Nations, 2020). In recent years, however, e-government framework has broadened to include the use of ICT for conducting a wide range of government interactions. For instance, Government-to-Government (G2G) platforms involve electronic exchanges between inter and intra-governmental actors while Government-to-Business (G2B) platforms involve business-specific transactions such as tax payment, license applications and other business-focused services. Moreover, Government-to-Citizen (G2C) platforms involve people's interaction with the government as consumers of public services such as provision of passports, driving licenses, birth certificates and land registrations.

In Kenya, the vision to realize e-government strategy in every public sector is one of the government's major priorities. According to Kenya National ICT survey (2018), the country has made improvements in areas of application of e-government for service delivery. Notably, the government has introduced projects such as Huduma Centres to act as one-stop shop for various government services. A report by the ICT Ministry (2019),

indicated that Kenya focuses on transforming itself into a nation where citizens have access and capability to thrive in the changing digital economy.

2. Statement of the problem

Studies have shown that many countries have made progress in implementation of e-government strategies in the public sector. Many studies have equally recognized that in some countries, especially the developing nations, implementation of e-government for everyday public service delivery has never been fully realized. Despite this recognition, there is still lack of empirical literature focusing on mediating and moderating variables that affect the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the public sector. Lack of such literature has limited the scope of researchers' understanding of the role of mediating and moderating variables on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery. This study sought to bridge this gap, by empirically examining the mediating effect of human resource capacity and moderating effect of top management support on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery, with a focus on Kenya's public sector.

3. Methodology

The study utilized descriptive research design. Specifically, the study used means and standard deviations for descriptive analysis. The study also employed correlation and regression for inferential analysis in order to establish the mediating and moderating effects of human resource capacity and top management support respectively. A sample of 66 respondents obtained using Green's formula (1991) was used in the study. The respondents consisted of government-employed individuals in Migori

County in Kenya. Closed-ended questionnaires were used for data collection.

4. Results

4.1 Response Rate

Table 1: Response rate

Questionnaires	Number	Response Rate
Total delivered to respondents	66	
Returned and used for analysis	57	80.3%

Source: Research data, 2025

The response rate was 80.3%. This response rate was adequate for data analysis because it was above the recommended minimum rate of 50% (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003).

4.2 Reliability of data collection instruments

Table 2: instrument reliability

Item	Cronbach's alpha	Comment
E-government adoption	0.712	Reliable
Service delivery	0.812	Reliable
Human resource capacity	0.709	Reliable
Top management support	0.768	Reliable

Source: Research data, 2025

The results indicated that the values of Cronbach's alpha were above the recommended minimum value of 0.7. These results justified further data analysis because all the values of Cronbach's alpha were more than 0.70.

4.3 Respondents' Characteristics

Table 3: respondents' characteristics

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender: Male	36	63.2
Female	21	36.8
Age:		
Below 30	12	21.1
30-34	15	26.3
35-44	14	24.6
45-49	9	15.7
50 and above	7	12.3
Education level: Certificate	8	14.0
Diploma	17	29.7
Degree	26	45.5
Masters	5	9.0
Doctoral	1	1.8
Experience: Below 1 year	6	10.5
1-3 years	10	17.6
3-5 years	17	29.8
5-10 years	16	28.1
10 and above	8	14.0

Source: Research data, 2025

The demographic results showed that many respondents were between 30-50 years and had worked for more than 3 years. This shows that the respondents had capacity to interact with e-government services. A study by Amit, Arindam, & Rajit (2018), revealed that younger and experienced employees are more likely to use new innovations in the work place.

4.4 Descriptive analysis of independent variable: E-government

Table 4: descriptive results for e-government

Item	Statement	M	SD	N
Item1	Government agencies have accessible websites	3.15	0.936	57
Item2	Online communication channels are readily available	3.99	1.012	57
Item3	Online inter-agency integrations are interactive	3.67	1.005	57
Item4	Most information for public use is accessed online	4.01	0.898	57

Item5	Citizen needs are addressed through online platforms	3.89	1.134	57
Grand Mean		3.74		

Source: Research data, 2025

Majority of the respondents had the opinion that government agencies have accessible websites (M=3.15, SD=0.936). On online communication channels, the respondents agreed that the channels are readily available (M=3.99, SD=1.012). The respondents further indicated that online inter-agency integrations are interactive (M=3.67, SD=1.005). Related, the respondents concurred that most information for public use is accessed online (M=4.01, SD=0.898). Furthermore, the participants noted that the citizen needs are addressed through online platforms (M=3.89, SD=1.134). These findings are in agreement with those of Bagozzi (2017) which found that most governments are committed to adopting e-government.

4.5 Descriptive analysis of Dependent variable: Service delivery

Table 5: descriptive results for service delivery

Item	Statement	M	SD	N
Item1	E-government has improved quality of services	4.02	1.023	57
Item2	E-government has reduced cost of services	3.78	0.924	57
Item3	E-government has reduced the time of accessing services	3.66	1.660	57
Item4	E-government has improved efficiency	3.87	0.987	57
Item5	E-government has improved transparency in service delivery	3.00	1.171	57
Grand Mean		3.67		

Source: Research data, 2025

The respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which e-government influences service delivery in the Kenya's public sector. The respondents pointed out that e-government has improved quality of services (M=4.02, SD=1.023). The respondents agreed that e-government has reduced cost of services (M=3.78, SD=0.924). On time efficiency, the respondents also agreed that e-government has reduced the time of accessing services (M=3.66, SD=1.660). The respondents further noted that e-government has not only improved efficiency (M=3.87, SD=0.987), but also transparency in the provision of public services (M=3.00, SD=1.171). The findings support those of Abu-Shanab & Haider (2015); Kipchumba (2012) which established that e-government improves public sector service delivery.

4.6 Descriptive analysis of Mediating variable: Human resource capacity

Table 6: descriptive results for human resource capacity

Item	Statement	M	SD	N
Item1	Employees are confident of using e-government platforms	3.03	1.033	57
Item2	Employees have adequate skills in e-government applications	3.00	1.056	57
Item3	Employees have no problem exchanging electronic information	3.58	1.586	57
Item4	Employees are adaptable to changing innovative environments	3.01	1.287	57
Item5	Employees are motivated to work with e-government platforms	3.46	1.449	57
Grand Mean		3.22		

Source: Research data, 2025

On human resource capacity, the respondents were in agreement that employees are confident of using e-government platforms (M=3.03, SD=1.033). The respondents noted that employees have adequate skills in e-government applications (M=3.00, SD=1.056). On the other hand, the respondents agreed that employees have no problem exchanging electronic information (M=3.50, SD=1.586) and that employees are adaptable to changing innovative environments (M=3.01, SD=1.287). Finally, it was noted that employees are motivated to work with e-government platforms (M=3.46, SD=1.449). These findings are congruent with the findings by Kiplangat & Shisia (2015) which established that contemporary employees are knowledgeable and can work in diverse environments, including changing technologies.

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 7: descriptive results for top management support

Item	Statement	M	SD	N
Item1	Top management has a positive view towards e-government	3.02	1.165	57
Item2	Top management encourages people to use e-government	3.55	0.899	57
Item3	Top management timely provides government infrastructure	3.11	0.962	57
Item4	Top management formulates flexible government policies	3.89	1.127	57
Item5	Top management provides training in the use of e-government	3.08	1.158	57

The top management was shown to have a positive view towards e-government (M=3.02, SD=1.165). The respondents indicated that the top management encourages people to use e-government (M=3.55, SD=0.899). Moreover, the respondents pointed out that top management timely provides e-government infrastructure (M=3.11, SD=0.962). On policies, the respondents agreed that top management formulates flexible policies for e-government adoption (M=3.89, SD=1.127) and that the top management provides training in the use of e-government (M=3.08, SD=1.158).

4.8 Correlation analysis

Table 8: correlation result

		E-government Adoption	Human Resource Capacity	Top Management Support	Service Delivery
E-government Adoption	Pearson Correlation	1	.457**	.583**	.703**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	57	57	57	57
Human Resource Capacity	Pearson Correlation	.457**	1	.422**	.411**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	57	57	57	57
Top Management Support	Pearson Correlation	.583**	.422**	1	.479**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	57	57	57	57
Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.703**	.411**	.479**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	57	57	57	57

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research data, 2025

The correlation between e-government adoption and service delivery was found to be positive and strong, with a value of .703. The correlation between the mediating and moderating variables was .422, which was desirable, as it indicated that the variables were not highly correlated to the extent of affecting regression models used in the sections below.

4.9 Regression analysis of the Mediating Effect of Human Resource Capacity on the relationship between e-government Adoption and service delivery. Testing of the mediating effect was one of the two major objectives of this study. The mediation effect was evaluated step-by-step using Baron and Kenny (1986) approach. The regression model for each step was evaluated independently.

Step one for Model 1

The first regression involved regressing dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on the independent variable [E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)]. The regression model of this step was thus:

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where: Y= Service Delivery (ServDel), X₁ = E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)

The assumption of normality for this regression model was met, as indicated by the Normal Probability Plot. Most of the data points were on or close to the normal line. Assumption of linearity was also met as indicated by the plot of Standardized residuals against standardized predicted values. The data points were evenly distributed about 0.

Fig. 1: Step one for Model 1

Source: Research data, 2025

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.360
R Squared	.364
Anova	
F-Statistic	84.777
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	1, 148
Coefficients	
Constant	1.742
Beta, β ₁	.603
t-statistic	9.207
Sig.	.000

From the regression results, the model was established as follows:
 ServDel = 1.742 + 0.603EgovAdop + ε (i)

explained by other factors not included in this study. Since the p-value (p=0.000) was less than 0.05, then it was noted that there is a significant relationship between Service Delivery and E-government Adoption. The significant relationship allowed for further analysis of mediation effect in step 2.

The findings indicated that in the direct relationship when there is no any mediation effect of human resource capacity, 36 % of variation in service delivery is explained by e-government adoption. The rest of the variation is

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Step Two for Model 2

Step two involved regressing the mediating variable [Human Resource Capacity (HumResCap)] on the independent variable [E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)]. The normality and linearity assumptions of the regression model were met as indicated by the Scatterplot and Normal Probability plots in Figure 2 below. The regression model was given as:

$$Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Where: Y_2 = Human Resource Capacity (HumResCap), X_2 = E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)

Fig. 2: Step two for Model 2

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.204
R Squared	.209
Anova	
F-Statistic	39.104
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	1, 148
Coefficients	
Constant	2.152
Beta, β_2	.457
t-statistic	6.253
Sig.	.000

Source: Research data, 2025

Model 2 was rewritten as shown below based on the values in the Figure 2:
 $HumResCap = 2.152 + .457 EgovAdop + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (ii)$

The result shows that 20.9% of variation in Human Resource Capacity is explained by E-government Adoption. The findings also showed that there is a significant positive relationship between Human Resource Capacity and E-government Adoption. This is because the p-value was less than 0.05 and both F-statistic (39.104) and t-statistic (6.253) were greater than the critical

values at ($P < 0.05$). The coefficient of e-government adoption was greater than 0.

Step Three for Model 3

Step three involved regressing the dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on the mediating variable [Human Resource Capacity (HumResCap)]. Regression assumptions were tested using the plots indicated in Figure 3 below.

Fig. 3: Step Three for Model 3

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.164
R Squared	.169
Anova	
F-Statistic	30.164
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	1, 148
Coefficients	
Constant	2.303
Beta, β_3	.411
t-statistic	5.492
Sig.	.000

Source: Research data, 2025

The regression model for step 3 was given as:

$$Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

Where: Y_3 = Service Delivery (ServDel), X_3 = Human Resource Capacity (HumResCap). Based on the findings, then:

$$ServDel = 2.303 + .411 HumResCap + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

The coefficient of determination of .169 shows that 16.9% of variation in Service Delivery is explained by Human Resource Capacity. Moreover, the regression coefficient was found to be positive ($\beta_3 = .411$). The t-statistic of 5.492 at $P = 0.000 < 0.05$ indicated that there is a positive significant relationship between Service Delivery and Human Resource Capacity.

E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)] and mediating variable [Human Resource Capacity

(HumResCap)]. The data points in the scatterplot do not funnel out and are uniformly distributed about X and Y axes on the origin. This shows that linearity assumption was met. Similarly, the data points on the Normal Probability plot are close to the normal line, indicating that normality assumption was met in this process.

The Model 4 was given as:

$$Y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

Where: Y_4 = Service Delivery (ServDel), X_4 = E-government Adoption (EgovAdop), X_5 = Human Resource Capacity (HumResCap)

Step Four for Model 4

Step four involved regressing the dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on both the independent variable

Fig. 4: Step Three for Model 4

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.379
R Squared	.384
Anova	
F-Statistic	46.488
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	2, 147
Coefficients	
Constant	1.386
Beta, β_4 (E-government Adoption)	.525
Beta, β_5 (Human Resource Capacity)	.171
t-statistic (E-government Adoption)	7.235
t-statistic (Human Res. Capacity)	2.361
Sig. (E-government Adoption)	.000
Sig. (Human Res. Capacity)	.020

Source: Research data, 2025

$$ServDel = 1.386 + .525 EgovAdop + .171 HumResCap + \epsilon \text{ (iv)}$$

The results show that E-government adoption would lead to a change of .525 in Service delivery if other factors are held constant. On the other hand, Human Resource Capacity would lead to a change of 1.71 in Service

delivery if other factors are held constant. The values of t-statistics at $p < 0.05$ showed that the relationship of e-government adoption and human resource capacity with service delivery is positively significant.

Table 9: Summary of mediation regression

Models	Decision criteria by Baron and Kenny (1986)	Current Research Findings	Comment
Model 1: $Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$ or $ServDel = 1.742 + 0.603EgovAdop + \epsilon$	If β_1 is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, there is still no conclusion of mediated relationship. However, the relationship is significant enough to be mediated	$(\beta_1 = 0.603, p = 0.000 < 0.05)$ is significant	Conclusion about mediating effect cannot be made
Model 2: $Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \epsilon$ or $HumResCap = 2.152 + 0.457 EgovAdop + \epsilon$	If β_2 is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, mediation effect exists	$(\beta_2 = 0.457, p = 0.000 < 0.05)$ is significant	Mediation effect of human resource capacity exists
Model 3: $Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$ or $ServDel = 2.303 + .411HumResCap + \epsilon$	If β_3 is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, mediation effect exists	$(\beta_3 = 0.411, p = 0.000 < 0.05)$ is significant	Mediation effect of human resource capacity exists
Model 4: $Y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \epsilon$ or $ServDel = 1.386 + .525 EgovAdop + .171 HumResCap + \epsilon$	If both β_4 & β_5 are significant at $P \leq 0.05$, partial mediation exists	$(\beta_4 = 0.525, p = 0.000 < 0.05; \beta_5 = 0.171, p = 0.020 < 0.05)$ are significant	Human resource capacity partially mediates the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery
Model 4: $Y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \epsilon$ or $ServDel = 1.386 + .525 EgovAdop + .171 HumResCap + \epsilon$	If β_4 is significant at $P > 0.05$ & β_5 is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, full mediation exists	$(\beta_4 = 0.525, p = 0.000 < 0.05; \beta_5 = 0.171, p = 0.020 < 0.05)$ are significant	Full mediation of human resource capacity does not exist

Source: Research data, 2025

The results in Table 9 show that human resource capacity has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public service.

4.9 Regression analysis of the Moderating Effect of Top management support on the relationship between e-government Adoption and service delivery.

The steps proposed by Whisman & McClelland (2005) and Fairchild, MacKinnon & Fritz (2009) were used to determine moderating effect of Top management support on the relationship between e-government Adoption and service delivery.

Step one for Model 1

The first regression involved regressing dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on the independent variable [E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)]. The regression model of this step was thus:

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where: Y= Service Delivery (ServDel), X_1 = E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)

The assumption of normality for this regression model was met, as indicated by the Normal Probability Plot. Most of the data points were on or close to the normal line. Assumption of linearity was also met as indicated by the plot of Standardized residuals against standardized predicted values. The data points were evenly distributed about 0.

Fig. 5: Step one for Model 1

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.360
R Squared	.364
Anova	
F-Statistic	84.777
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	1, 148
Coefficients	
Constant	1.742
Beta, β_1	.603
t-statistic	9.207
Sig.	.000

Source: Research data, 2025

From the regression results, the model was established as follows:

$$\text{ServDel} = 1.742 + 0.603\text{EgovAdop} + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

The findings indicated that in the direct relationship when there is no any mediation effect of human resource capacity, 36 % of variation in service delivery is explained by e-government adoption. The rest of the variation is explained by other factors not included in this study. Since the p-value ($p=0.000$) was less the 0.05, then it was noted that there is a significant relationship between Service Delivery and E-government Adoption. The significant relationship allowed for further analysis of mediation effect in step 2.

Step Two for Model 2

Step two involved regressing the dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on both the independent variable [E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)] and moderating variable [Top Management Support (TopManSup)]. The normality and linearity assumptions of the regression model were met as indicated by the Scatterplot and Normal Probability plots in Figure 6 below. The regression model was given as:
 $Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (ii)$
 Where: Y_2 = Service Delivery (ServDel), X_2 = E-govern. Adoption (EgovAdop), X_3 = Top Manag. Support (TopManSup).

Fig. 6: Step two for Model 2

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.381
R Squared	.389
Anova	
F-Statistic	46.778
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	2, 147
Coefficients	
Constant	1.478
Beta, β_2	.491
Beta, β_3	.193
t-statistic (E-government Adoption)	6.186
t-statistic (Top Management Support)	2.438
Sig. (E-government Adoption)	.000
Sig. (Top Management Support)	.106

Source: Research data, 2025

Model 2 was rewritten as shown below based on the values in the Figure2:

$$\text{ServDel} = \beta_0 + .491 \text{EgovAdop} + .193 \text{TopManSup} + \epsilon \dots \dots (ii)$$

The result shows that 38.9% of variation in Service Delivery is explained by E-government Adoption and Top Management Support. The findings also showed that there is a significant positive relationship between Service Delivery, E-government Adoption and Top Management Support. This is because both t-statistic (E-government Adoption, 6.186) and t-statistic (Top Management Support, 2.438) were greater than the critical values at

($P < 0.05$).

Step Three for Model 3

Step three involved regressing the dependent variable [Service Delivery (ServDel)] on the independent variable [E-government Adoption (EgovAdop)], moderating variable [Top Management Support (TopManSup)] and the Interaction Term [E-government Adoption* Top Management Support (EgovAdop* TopManSup)]. Regression assumptions were tested using the plots indicated in Figure 7 below.

Fig. 7: Step Three for Model 3

Model Summary	
Adjusted R Squared	.376
R Squared	.389
Anova	
F-Statistic	30.895
Sig.	.000 ^b
Df	3, 146
Coefficients	
Constant	1.342
Beta, β_4 (E-government Adoption)	.537
Beta, β_5 (Top Management Support)	.237
Beta, β_6 (Interaction Term)	-.080
t-statistic (E-government Adoption)	1.637
t-statistic (Top Management Support)	.766
t-statistic (Interaction Term)	-.145
Sig. (E-government Adoption)	.104
Sig. (Top Management Support)	.445
Sig. (Interaction Term)	.885

Fig. Source: Research data, 2025

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The regression model for step 3 was given as:

$$Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{(iii)}$$

Where: Y_3 = Service Delivery (ServDel), X_4 = E-government Adoption (EgovAdop), X_5 = Top Management Support (TopManSup), X_6 = E-government Adoption* Top Management Support (EgovAdop* TopManSup)

Based on the findings, then:

$$\text{ServDel} = 2.303 + .537\text{EgovAdop} + .237\text{TopManSup} - .080\text{EgovAdop*TopManSu} + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{(iii)}$$

The coefficient of determination of .376 shows that 37.6% of variation in Service Delivery is explained by E-government adoption, Top Management Support and the Interaction Term.

Summary of Moderation Models and Decision criteria

Table 10: summary of moderation regression models

Models	Decision criteria by Whisman and McClelland (2005); Fairchild and MacKinnon (2009)	Current Research Findings	Comment
Model 1: $Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$ or $\text{ServDel} = 1.742 + 0.603\text{EgovAdop} + \epsilon$	If β_1 is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, there is still no conclusion of mediated relationship. However, the relationship is significant enough to be moderated	$(\beta_1 = 0.603, p = 0.000 < 0.05)$ is significant	Conclusion about moderation effect cannot be made
Model 2: $Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$ or $\text{ServDel} = \beta_0 + .491 \text{EgovAdop} + .193 \text{TopManSup} + \epsilon$	If β_2 is significant ($p \leq 0.05$) and β_3 is not significant ($p > 0.05$), the moderating variable is an explanatory variable	$(\beta_2 = 0.491, p = 0.000 < 0.05$ and $\beta_3 = 0.193, p = 0.106 > 0.05$) are significant	Top Management Support is an explanatory variable. It does not have moderating effect
Model 3: $Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \epsilon$ or $\text{ServDel} = 2.303 + .537\text{EgovAdop} + .237\text{TopManSup} - .080\text{EgovAdop*TopManSu} + \epsilon$	If β_4 and β_6 are both significant at $p \leq 0.05$ then the moderating variable has a moderating effect	$(\beta_4 = 0.537, p = 0.104 > 0.05$ and $\beta_6 = -0.080, p = 0.885 > 0.05)$ are not significant	Moderating effect of Top Management Support does not exist

Source: Research data, 2025

The results in Table 10 show that human resource capacity has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public service.

5. Conclusion

The study sought to investigate the mediating effect of human resource capacity and moderating effect of top management support on the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in Kenya's public sector. The study found that human resource capacity partially mediates the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery while top management support does not moderate the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery. The study concluded that human resource capacity is a mediating variable while top management support is an explanatory variable in the context of e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public sector.

6. Limitation of this study

This study focused only on human resource capacity as the mediating factor and top management support as the moderating factor in the relationship between e-government adoption and service delivery in Kenya's public sector. The study therefore did not analyze other factors (such as the government policy) that could have moderating or mediating effect on e-government adoption and service delivery.

7. Recommendations for future studies

The future studies should explore other potential mediating and moderating factors in the relationship between e-government and service delivery. The future studies should also use larger samples and other statistical methods to examine the mediating and moderating factors in the link between e-government adoption and service delivery in the Kenya's public sector.

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